

3D Structural Characterization and Performance Assessment of Lime-cement Mortars During Salt Damage

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Abstract. Six lime-cement mortar mixtures were created to compare their structural properties and study their durability after being contaminated with a 5% NaCl solution. NaCl is a common salt found in modern buildings causing an efflorescence effect and thereby impacting not only the aesthetics of the walls, but also influence the internal structures by subflorescence, triggering serious damage and eventual failure. To have a better understanding of the salt crystallization in lime-cement mortars, 3D micro-computed tomography models were obtained before and after salt contamination and during accelerated aging of the lime-based mortars to analyze and compare the 3D micro-structures and the resulting salt crystallization in a non-destructive way. This was validated by the physical and chemical characterization of each mixture and their byproducts by means of SEM-EDX, XRD and MIP.

Keywords: lime mortars, efflorescence, subflorescence, micro-CT, 3D characterization, non-destructive imaging, salt crystallization.

1 Introduction

Lime mortars have been widely used in construction for the past ~ 6 millennia. Nevertheless, they have slowly been replaced by Portland Cement mortars since the 20th century due to their faster hardening and greater strength [1], leaving lime mortars mostly as the go-to materials for restoration of heritage buildings. This research intends to bridge the gap between lime and cement mortars by studying their structure and performance, in order to determine their suitability for modern construction and for restoration purposes. Additionally, the behavior of these mortars towards salt crystallization is analyzed. This phenomenon has been previously investigated, yielding a number of European standards and international recommendations [2]. Nevertheless, these protocols focus on rocks, bricks, and masonry units [2, 3], without particular regard of soft, porous materials such as lime-based mortars, and are proven to be too aggressive and inconsistent with real damage caused by salts on masonry [2]. Therefore, the RILEM Technical Committee ASC-271 [4] has developed some suggestions to execute a more reliable and efficient test for accelerated salt crystallization which will also be used in this study.

2 Materials and Methods

Hydrated lime (CL90S) and CEM II/A-L 32.5R cement were used for the manufacturing of 6 lime-cement mortar combinations to test their performance (Table 1). The test specimens were prepared in accordance to EN 1015-11:2019 [5].

To test structural performance, 120 standard size specimens (4x4x16 cm) were manufactured (Table 1). The development of their compressive and flexural strength was evaluated at 7, 14, 21, 28 and 90 days according to EN 196-1:2016 [6] for comparison between the distinct mixtures. Additionally, 18 standard size samples underwent water absorption by capillarity to obtain their water absorption coefficient (WAC) following EN 1925:1999 [7]. Cylindrical mortar samples were cast into shape (type A: 5 cm \varnothing x 5 cm, type B: 2.5 \varnothing x 2.5 cm, and type C: 1.3 cm \varnothing x 1.8 cm) to perform a multi-scale analyses. 18 type A samples were used for open porosity tests in accordance to EN 1936:2007 [8]. Additional tests using Mercury Intrusion Porosimetry (MIP, Thermo Fisher Scientific) were performed on fractions of each mixture to evaluate their porosity and pore size distribution. The experimental protocol for salt crystallization development by RILEM TC ASC-271 was performed on 4 cylindrical samples per mortar mixture (types A, B, and C), using a solution of 5% NaCl, to assess their salt solution transport properties and accumulation of salts at the drying surface. Subsequently, the specimens were subjected to 3 cycles of accelerated weathering, using temperature and relative humidity cycles ranging from 20-40°C and 15-95% RH. Damage was photographically documented with a Leica microscope (x20) and a digital camera (Canon EOS 440D). Constant weight monitoring was recorded to track mass variations during drying and rewetting steps. The resulting damage products (mainly powder) were collected, finely ground and analyzed by means of XRD (Bruker) for the identification of the mineral phases. Elemental mapping was done on the surface of 4 type B samples to assess the distribution of the salts in the different mixtures using a FEG-SEM-EDX (TESCAN). Cross sections perpendicular to the drying surface of type A contaminated samples were additionally mapped to estimate the penetration depth of salts from the drying front. Type C samples were scanned at a 12 μm resolution (120 kV, 10W, exposure time 1.0 s) using the lab-based micro-X-ray CT scanner HECTOR [9] before and after contamination, and after the third weathering cycle to analyze the 3D pore network and the potential internal damage caused by the salt crystallization in a non-destructive way [10]. Further rendering and image analysis was done on Avizo and Fiji software.

3 Results and Discussion

Strength results indicated an improvement after 7 to 28 days (Table 1). For the improvement of the properties of 1:0:3 samples, the curing protocol was modified and the mortars were put in a carbonation chamber at 1% CO₂ for 14 days, thus improving the compressive and flexural strength to 3.97 N/mm² and 1.27 N/mm² respectively. The WAC's are in line with the open porosity results. The experimental salt crystallization protocol yielded information on the behavior of the distinct mixtures. The average mass

gains of 4 repetitions per mixture were recorded in Table 1. Physical changes were also observed due to subflorescence and efflorescence (Fig. 1).

Table 1. Lime:cement:sand (L:C:S) and water-to-binder ratios (by volume) used according to standard curing conditions (EN 1015-11:2019), water absorption coefficients by EN 1925:1999 (WAC, %), open porosity (OP, %) by EN 1936:2007, mass gain (%), and flexural (F_f) and compressive (F_c) strength by EN 196-1:2016 after 7/28 days (N/mm^2).

	1:0:3	4:1:15	2:1:9	1:1:6	1:2:9	0:1:3
w/b ratio	0.8	0.8	0.75	0.725	0.725	0.7
WAC	154.40	242.14	217.94	136.37	84.30	37.54
OP (%)	26.26	26.07	25.54	25.24	24.86	24.99
Mass gain	0.60	2.36	1.34	1.20	1.51	1.50
7d F_f	0.00	0.13	0.59	1.48	2.44	4.96
28d F_f	0.20	0.65	0.92	2.09	3.91	6.51
7d F_c	0.00	2.18	3.04	6.77	12.80	34.34
28d F_c	0.00	2.48	4.53	8.99	18.36	34.41

The superficial loose material, induced by salt crystallization, was collected after the second and third weathering cycle and analyzed by XRD. Here, quartz, feldspars, micas, calcite, trace amounts of gypsum, and halite diffraction patterns were identified. The powder samples of the second weathering cycle showed a higher amount of halite, compared to those of the third cycle due to salt migration towards the surface in the first and second stages of weathering. The test also indicates that subflorescence caused inner stress and loss of cohesion of the quartz grains and the calcitic binder.

Fig. 1. 1:0:3 mortar sample after salt contamination and different weathering cycles.

Elemental mapping by FEG-SEM-EDX on type B samples (4:1:15) showed an accumulation of Na and Cl, particularly surrounding the quartz grains (Fig. 2-A), whereas the predominantly cement samples such as 1:1:6, displayed a lower concentration of Na and Cl (Fig. 2-B). This is probably linked to the samples' distinct pore network and the resulting location of salt crystallization. Additionally, the elemental mapping of the cross section of a 1:2:9 type A sample clearly showed a higher concentration of NaCl on the 5 mm below the drying face, which confirmed a successful salt accumulation process. The μ CT image analysis of the 1:1:6 type C sample showed deterioration after the weathering cycles (Fig. 2-C-D) and displays material loss towards the drying front compared to the sample before contamination (Fig. 2-C).

Fig. 2. SEM-EDX elemental mapping of type B samples 4:1:15 (A) and 1:1:6 (B), Na=yellow, Cl=green, Ca=cyan; X-ray CT rendering of a 1:1:6 type C sample before contamination (C) and after 3 weathering cycles (D) where the dotted line indicates the original surface, and arrows show the location of the greater material loss.

4 Conclusions

A number of challenges are present on multi-scale analysis, especially on small mortar samples. However, first experiments are promising. Further image analysis is needed to study in detail subflorescence and its impact on the larger scale, as well as to fully comprehend the relationship between the pore network and salt transport through it, exploiting the invaluable advantages that 3D micro-CT analysis provides.

The SUBLime project received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research & innovation program under MSCA project SUBLime [Grant Agreement n 955986].

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